

CONTROL OF RESIN FLOW USING MULTIFUNCTIONAL INTERDIGITAL ELECTRODE ARRAY FILM DURING LCM

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1. Introduction

To prevent dry spots occurring during the vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process, resin flow simulation to optimize resin inlet or outlet location is usually conducted. However, any slight differences in the wrinkle of the vacuum bag or misalignment of the fabric preform cause unexpected resin flow, even if the mold conditions such as temperature, preform type, and vacuum pressure are set to be the same. This unexpected resin flow causes dry spots including small voids, which significantly deteriorate the mechanical properties of the structure [1-3]. Because of the poor quality of the VaRTM process, its application to aerospace structures is currently limited. Consequently, monitoring dry spots and methods are essential, to prevent their occurrence in real time during the VaRTM process.

To prevent dry spots by altering resin flow in real time, pressure regulators between the mold and vacuum pumps have been used to change the pressure distribution [4-7]. This method, however, usually requires many inlet or outlet points, and it is difficult to control the flow far from the inlet or outlet points. Johnson *et al.* proposed a coil induction heating method [8, 9], which decreased the resin viscosity via heating and thereby controlled the resin flow. This method requires a carbon susceptor and large *x-y* stage that covers the whole mold for scanning, and is not applicable to structures without the susceptor or to complicated curved surface structures. The high cost and inflexible equipment may counteract the advantage of low cost and easy-to-use manufacturing in VaRTM.

In the present study, we propose a flow control scheme using the thin smart film to actuate the resin flow as well as monitoring resin flow and temperature. The film works multifunctionally as

actuator and sensor for resin flow and temperature; thus the film is named a multifunctional interdigital electrode array (MIEA; Fig. 1). The validity of the proposed flow control scheme was investigated by manufacturing cored GFRP structures by LCM.

2. Area-sensor array for monitoring of resin flow

The sensor had capacitive interdigital electrodes [10-12]. Each sensor had a squared sensing area, and the impedance of the sensor changed to correspond with the impregnated area ratio of the sensor area. This enabled us to measure the area impregnated with resin for each squared section. The entire film surface was covered with these squared interdigital electrodes without any un-sensing space; thus it allowed the full-field monitoring of the resin flow, and was expected to identify the precise flow front and detect any small dry spots that occurred anywhere on the film.

(a) Overview of obverse

(b) Interdigital electrodes on the obverse and wiring on the reverse side.

Fig. 1 Area-sensor array film for full field monitoring of resin flow.

3. Scheme of full-field flow monitoring

Using the impregnated area ratios of each area sensor, the flow front is estimated to match the estimated impregnated area and each measured impregnated area ratio as shown in Fig. 2. The impregnation factor F_{ij} at sensor $i-j$ is defined as

$$F_{ij} = \frac{\Delta|Z_{ij}(S_1/S, T)|}{\Delta|Z_{ij}(1, T)|}. \quad (1)$$

The factor F_{ij} corresponds to S_1/S : 0 before impregnation, and 1 at full impregnation of the sensor $i-j$. By measuring the value $\Delta|Z(1, T)|$ using the same electrode beforehand, real-time measuring of F_{ij} is possible.

We know the impregnated area ratios at each sensor area by obtaining the impregnation factor F_{ij} at each electrode. Next, using the factor F_{ij} , cubic spline interpolation is conducted, and we obtain the surface of the factor $F(x, y)$ at an arbitrary location where the $x-y$ coordinate is defined on the in-plane of the film as shown in Fig. 3. It is assumed that the impregnated area figuration of one sensor is affected by the adjacent impregnated sensor area, and the flow front is a smooth curve.

The area of $F(x, y)$ over the threshold F_t in the sensor $i-j$ domain corresponds to the estimated impregnated area ratio $FE_{ij}(F_t)$ in the sensor $i-j$:

$$FE_{ij}(F_t) = \frac{\iint_{\Omega} dx dy}{S_{ij}}, \quad \Omega = \{(x, y) \in \text{sensor } i-j \text{ domain} \mid F(x, y) > F_t\} \quad (2)$$

where S_{ij} is the sensor $i-j$ area.

Finally we determine the threshold F_t by minimizing the residual sum of squares between the measured impregnated area ratio F_{ij} and estimated impregnated area ratio $FE_{ij}(F_t)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } S_e(F_t) &= \sum_{i=1}^S \sum_{j=A}^E (F_{ij} - FE_{ij}(F_t))^2 \\ \text{subject to } &0 \leq F_t \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In this method, the measured impregnated area ratio F_{ij} is 0.6, for example, using the impedance change ratio at one sensor, the estimated impregnated area is drawn with a smooth line and has 60 % impregnation of the sensor region. Thus the estimated impregnated area matches the measured impregnated area ratio using the area-sensor array. The area that is not impregnated, where F_{ij} is less than 1.0, is never ignored, and small dry spots will be detected.

Fig. 2 Relationship between impedance change ratio and impregnated area.

Fig. 3 The schema for identifying the impregnated area.

4.1 In-plane and out-of-plane impregnation

Figure 4 shows the two types of resin impregnation during the VaRTM process. In the case of thin laminates without a distribution medium, the dry fabrics are impregnated with resin from the side (in-plane impregnation), and the flow in the thickness direction is negligible as shown in Fig. 4 (a). In this case, the dry spot will penetrate in the thickness direction, and the precise flow front can be estimated using a sensor array film.

On the other hand, if a resin distribution medium is used to enhance the resin impregnation or in the case of through-thickness injection, the resin flows in the through-thickness direction (out-of-plane impregnation) exist as shown in Fig. 4 (b), the dry spot does not penetrate in the thickness direction. To draw the precise dry spot configuration, the impregnated thickness must be estimated at each sensor. However, the method proposed in the previous study uses only the single parameter of impedance, thus it cannot identify the difference between in-plane and out-of-plane impregnation.

Fig. 4 Resin impregnation during the RTM: (a) in-plane impregnation and (b) out-of-plane impregnation.

The electrical capacitance and resistance are measured when using glass cloth fabric impregnated with resin by in-plane or out-of-plane impregnation. The LCR meter (Hioki, 3532-50) is used for measuring the capacitance and electric resistance at 800 Hz. Figure 5 shows the experimental setup. One $35 \times 35 \text{ mm}^2$ sensor is stacked on the acrylic plate. It should be noted that in the case of using a metallic mold, it is required to cover the electrode wires on the bottom surface of the sensor film with non-conductive thin layer. Eight layers of the 1K (1000 filaments/strand) glass fabric (Molymer SSP, YEM1801) are stacked on the sensor film, and an unsaturated polyester resin (DH material, Sundhoma PC-184-C) is impregnated. In the out-of-lane impregnation, the PVDC film (0.01 mm thickness) is inserted between the layers to separate the impregnated and un-impregnated layers. Electric capacitance and resistance are measured for four types of impregnated states: before impregnation, 1 layer impregnation, 7 layers impregnation, and full (8 layers, the thickness is about 2.0 mm) impregnation.

Fig. 5 Experimental setup for measuring the electrical resistance and capacitance for out-of-plane impregnation.

4.2 Experimental results and discussion

Figure 6 shows the electrical capacitance and resistance in the case of in-plane impregnation. The plots indicate the experimental capacitance and resistance change ratio $C_{\text{exp}}/C_{\text{exp}_0}$ and $R_{\text{exp}}/R_{\text{exp}_0}$ where C_{exp_0} and R_{exp_0} are the experimental initial capacitance and resistance before impregnation. The abscissa indicates the impregnated length divided by the sensor length: $L = 0$ is the un-impregnated and $L = 1$ is the fully impregnated state. The electric resistance decreases drastically when the resin touches a part of the inter-digital electrode, whereas the capacitance increase is almost proportional to the impregnated length L . This is because the resistivity ratio ρ_G/ρ_R is very high and the impregnated and un-impregnated glass fiber fabric can be modeled as a parallel circuit of electrical resistance. On the other hand, the permittivity ratio ϵ_G/ϵ_R is not as high and a drastic change does not occur if the resin touches the electrode.

The plots in Fig. 7 show the experimental electrical capacitance and resistance in the case of out-of-plane impregnation from the top to the bottom layer. The abscissa indicates the impregnated thickness divided by the composite thickness: $T = 0$ is un-impregnated and $T = 1$ is the fully impregnated state. In the case of out-of-plane impregnation, the electrical resistance decreases and the capacitance increases gradually. The gradual decrease of the

electrical resistance is derived from the series circuit model of electrical resistance of resin and glass fiber fabrics even when the resistivity ratio ρ_G/ρ_R is very high: one drastic electrical resistance decrease does not significantly affect the combined overall resistance.

Fig. 6 Capacitance and resistance change ratio of experimental and calculated results using the equivalent circuit model during in-plane impregnation.

Fig. 7 Capacitance and resistance change ratio of experimental and calculated results using the equivalent circuit model during out-of-plane impregnation.

5.1 Flow control using dielectric heating

The flow velocity of resin inside the mold through the fiber preform during the LCM process can be assumed to follow Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{U} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\phi\mu} \nabla P \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{U} is flow velocity vector, \mathbf{K} is preform permeability tensor, ϕ is porosity, μ is resin viscosity, and ∇P is gradient of pressure. We focus on flow velocity control by viscosity change of the resin based on Eq. (4), by raising the resin temperature. The relationship between viscosity and the temperature until cure starts is

$$\mu = \mu_{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{U}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

where μ_{∞} is the viscosity at infinite temperature, U is activation energy, R is the universal gas constant, and T is absolute temperature.

5.2 Flow velocity increase using dielectric heating

The resin temperature can be raised by dielectric heating using the MIEA. When a dielectric material such as polyester resin is placed in the electric field, the dipoles of the resin align with the electric field direction, and polarization occurs as shown in Fig. 8. When the frequency of the electric field is much faster than the rotation of the dipole, the movement cannot follow and frictional heating between dipoles occurs. This dielectric heating has the advantages 1) uniform heating is possible, unlike the situation using external heating equipment, because the dielectric material itself heats; 2) selective heating is also possible by controlling the electric field.

The heating value P is expressed as

$$P = VI \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \delta\right) \quad (6)$$

where V is voltage, I is current and δ is loss angle.

The dielectric material has $\delta \ll 1$, hence

$$P = VI \sin \delta \approx VI \tan \delta \quad (7)$$

where $\tan \delta$ is loss tangent, and $\tan \delta \approx 0.05$ for the UP resin that was used at 1000 Hz. Since the equivalent circuit of the MIEA is modeled as a parallel resistor and capacitor, the capacitor component is expressed as

$$C = \varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \frac{S}{d} \quad (8)$$

where ε_r is relative permittivity, ε_0 is the permittivity in vacuum, S is electrode area, and d is the distance between the electrodes. The electric current I flowing in the capacitor is

$$I = 2\pi f CV = 2\pi f \varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \frac{S}{d} V \quad (9)$$

where f is frequency. By substituting Eq. (9) in Eq. (7), the heating value P is

$$P = 2\pi \varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \frac{S}{d} f V^2 \tan \delta \quad (10)$$

From this equation, to obtain higher heating value higher frequency and voltage are required. To satisfy this demand, the waveform generator (NF, WF1943) outputs a high frequency wave of 10 MHz and 14 V_{pp}; then is amplified by an amplifier (NF, HSA4101) to 142 V_{pp} that is the maximum of the instrument; is again amplified to 200-300 V_{pp} using a self-made high frequency transformer with an Ni-Zn ferrite core as shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8 Behavior of dipole in dielectric polymer impressed by electric field.

(a) Dielectric heating with a interdigital electrode.

(b) High frequency transformer

(c) Circuit of high frequency transformer

Fig. 9 Device for flow control by dielectric heating.

6 Estimation of resin temperature distribution

6.1 Theory

Since the resin temperature is raised for flow control, impedance measurement for flow monitoring was affected by the increasing temperature. The impedance change $\Delta|Z(1,T)|/|Z_0|$ measured using MIEA when the Sundhoma PC-184-C resin temperature rises. The impedance decreased as the resin temperature increased, thus the MIEA may estimate a larger resin impregnation area than the actual area during the dielectric heating. To solve this problem, the resin temperature distribution was estimated using MIEA for temperature compensation.

The temperature distribution was obtained using the frequency dependence of permittivity of a polar polymer. Since the rotation of the electric dipoles during orientational polarization is delayed owing to viscous resistance, the polar polymer shows the frequency dependence of permittivity caused by dielectric relaxation. The complex permittivity, ϵ^* , is expressed by Eq. (11) using the relaxation time, τ , and alternating current frequency, ω [13].

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{1 + i\omega\tau} \quad (11)$$

where ϵ_∞ and $\Delta\epsilon$ are the permittivity at infinite frequency and relaxation strength, respectively. The real part, ϵ' , of the complex permittivity is given by

$$\epsilon' = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{1 + \omega^2\tau^2} \quad (12)$$

At high frequency, Eq. (12) can be approximated as Eq. (13) for $\omega^2\tau^2 \gg 1$

$$\epsilon' \approx \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\omega^2\tau^2} \quad (13)$$

By means of a Taylor series expansion around ω_0 , Eq. (13) can be rewritten as

$$\epsilon' \approx \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{\omega_0^2\tau^2} - \frac{2\Delta\epsilon}{\omega_0^3\tau^2} \Delta\omega = b_0 + b_1\Delta\omega \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ represents a minute change in frequency, and b_0 and b_1 correspond to $\varepsilon_\infty + \Delta\varepsilon/\omega_0^2\tau^2$ and $-2\Delta\varepsilon/\omega_0^3\tau^2$, respectively. If $\Delta\omega$ is up to several kHz, Eq. (14) is a good approximation. Using the constant m from Eq. 12,

$$\tau = \frac{m}{\sqrt{-b_1}} \quad (15)$$

where $m = \sqrt{2\Delta\varepsilon/\omega_0^3}$. According to the Rouse principle [14], the relaxation time τ_T is

$$\tau_T = \frac{6\mu_T M}{\pi^2 \rho RT} \quad (16)$$

where μ_T is viscosity at temperature T , M is molecular weight, and ρ is density.

Using the relaxation time τ_{T_0} at temperature T_0 and density ρ_0 ,

$$\frac{\tau_T}{\tau_{T_0}} = \frac{\mu_T \rho_0 T_0}{\mu_{T_0} \rho T} \quad (17)$$

where μ_{T_0} is the viscosity at temperature T_0 .

As the fractional temperature and density variations are infinitesimal compared with the fractional viscosity variation, $(T\rho/T_0\rho_0)$ can be approximated as 1. Thus the following relation is constructed between relaxation time τ and viscosity μ using constant n

$$\mu = \frac{\mu_{T_0}}{\tau_{T_0}} \tau = \frac{\mu_{T_0}}{\tau_{T_0}} \cdot \frac{m}{\sqrt{-b_1}} = \frac{n}{\sqrt{-b_1}} \quad (18)$$

where $n = \frac{\mu_{T_0}}{\tau_{T_0}} m$.

Here, the viscosity μ of the thermosetting resin depends on the absolute temperature T and degree of curing β , and is represented as [15, 16]

$$\mu = \mu_\infty \exp\left(\frac{U}{RT} + K\beta\right) \quad (19)$$

where K is a material constant. Thus, the viscosity index $1/\sqrt{-b_1}$ is given by

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-b_1}} = \frac{\mu_\infty}{n} \exp\left(\frac{U}{RT} + K\beta\right). \quad (20)$$

Since resin impregnation finishes before curing starts in VaRTM, the degree of cure $\beta=0$. Equation (20) is solved for temperature T as

$$T = \frac{U}{R} \cdot \frac{1}{\ln\left(\frac{1/\sqrt{-b_1}}{\mu_\infty/n}\right)} \quad (21)$$

This equation indicates that the temperature can be calculated from measurements of the viscosity index $1/\sqrt{-b_1}$. b_1 corresponds to the frequency dependence of the resin permittivity, and is calculated from Eq. (14) by measuring the capacitance at multiple frequencies. The material constants μ_∞/n and U/R in Eq. (21) can be obtained by exponential approximation of the viscosity index $1/\sqrt{-b_1}$ and the inverse of absolute temperature $(1/T)$.

7 LCM flow control experiments

7.1 Experimental procedures

The area-sensor array film is placed on the acrylic plate and eight layers of 1K glass cloth (Molymer SSP, YEM1801) are stacked on the film. The urethane foam core is inserted between the fourth and fifth layer. This model structure simulates the keel structures of marine vessels. The experiments were carried out by impregnating the glass fabric with unsaturated polyester resin (DH material, Sundhoma PC-184-C). The resin heating was conducted using wave generator, amplifier, and high frequency transformer as shown in Fig. 9

7.2 Results and discussion

Fig. 10(a) shows resin impregnation without flow control, taken by video camera through the bottom acrylic plate on the left. It was observed that the resin flow under the urethane foam core was delayed compared with the side areas. The two flows on both sides of the foam core impregnated faster

than the central flow around the core region, and the two side flows touched before the center area was impregnated with resin. Consequently, a dry spot occurred around the core region.

Fig. 10(b) shows the results of flow monitoring and controlling by dielectric heating. By comparing the time history of resin impregnation with/without flow control, due to the dielectric heating, the flow velocity increased at the core center region, the flow delay at the central region was alleviated, and occurrence of the dry spot was prevented.

Fig. 10 Impregnation view, (a) without control and (b) with control using MIEA.

8. Conclusions

The present study proposes a flow control scheme by monitoring and actuating resin flow/temperature using thin MIEA film during a LCM process. The capacitive interdigital electrodes on the MIEA were adopted as the sensor for monitoring resin flow front. The method increases the resin velocity by increasing the resin temperature at the appropriate locations to prevent dry spots. Foam cored GFRP structures were manufactured in LCM, and the effectiveness of flow control was investigated by comparing with and without flow

control. As a result, the occurrence of dry spot was prevented with flow control, whereas dry spot occurred without flow control.

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